

The Role and Importance of Pedagogical Technologies in Improving the Professional Competence of Teachers

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Abstract:

This article discusses the role and benefits of educational technology in enhancing the professional competencies of science teachers in schools. The effective use of pedagogical technologies in the formation of professional competencies of teachers and in the educational process is also mentioned.

Keywords: competence, teacher, activity, innovation, education, technology, problem, education, profession, skill, qualification, teacher, interactive, lifelong education,

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Introduction

Today, modern pedagogical processes based on the creation, assimilation and dissemination of innovations in the field of education are organized in an open, flexible, individualized, creating new knowledge. It is clear that the formation of new educational technologies - technological innovations, new economic mechanisms in education - economic innovations, new methods of teaching - pedagogical innovations, new organizational structures - organizational innovations, as well as their unity. thousands. Systematic work is underway to develop the knowledge economy by creating an innovative pedagogical environment in leading higher education institutions. In the context of globalization and internationalization of education in the world, research is being conducted to improve the mechanisms of training managers for innovative activities on the basis of optimizing strategic and functional management, expanding the pedagogical potential of innovation management, introduction of pedagogical innovations and evaluation of their effectiveness.

The world experience shows that the main directions in the organization of professional development of teachers are the development of a variable system of professional development aimed at ensuring its continuity and independent training through the adoption of modern educational technologies and new forms of professional development. considered.

The words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, "Bringing up our children as truly patriotic people with independent thinking, modern knowledge and professions, a strong life position, is a matter of great importance for all of us." After all, in the destiny of every person, his education in school, vocational colleges and universities is very important. Innovative pedagogical activity in scientific and educational institutions of the developed countries of the world is considered as an important direction of strategic development.

Therefore, the interest in the use of innovative technologies in the education system is growing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that while the goals of education have so far been to teach young people only ready-made knowledge, today modern technology allows them to search for their own knowledge and even draw their own conclusions.

Main part

Today, radical reforms are being carried out in the system of retraining and advanced training of teachers in the country. The years of independence have been marked by the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at defining the prospects of socio-economic and cultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, striving to take a worthy place in the world community. The study of the experience of the developed countries of the world, taking into account the local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of radical reforms in all spheres of society, provides new achievements. Although international cooperation in various fields is bearing fruit, the strengthening of national independence in all respects, the enrichment of achievements, the rapid elimination of existing shortcomings require special dedication, diligence, courage and requires determination.

Innovative technologies in the pedagogical process are innovations, changes in the activities of teachers and students, which require the use of interactive methods.

In particular, the use of innovative technologies in the classroom stimulates students' interest in scientific research, develops creativity and ingenuity. As a result, the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities will be applied in practice, the quality of mastering will increase. To do this, the teacher must be competent and plan the lesson correctly according to the content of the topics, to ensure that all students work actively and consciously during the lesson.

Today, the modern education system in our country is the result of the great changes that have taken place in this area in recent years. From this point of view, education is not only a part of the social life of today's society, but also one of the important factors in its development. It is well known that education is one of the key factors in educating the next generation.

As you know, innovation is a theoretically based, goal-oriented and practical innovation. Any innovation requires a high level of emotionality and intelligence. For these reasons, innovation in education is slowly gaining ground. The educational process in secondary schools and higher education institutions, as we have seen, requires innovative practice not only in active dialogue with the teacher, but also in being active and proactive in understanding the world. Today we see not only an innovative system of education, but also the activation of the mental state of teachers. Opinions about innovation processes, in our opinion, are grouped around the following questions: what is the difference, nature, nature of the innovation process; who is the subject of this process, how does this subject manifest itself; what problems solve innovative processes in education; which types are clearly visible; the teacher's awareness of innovations (psychological, methodological, cognitive) in the learning process; motivation of innovative processes in the educational institution; their role in educational technologies and educational reforms. The concept of "innovative education" is interpreted differently in the scientific literature: some authors look at innovation from a philosophical and theoretical point of view, while others understand the rational use of a factor in the learning process, such as active teaching methods or teaching aids. The essence of educational innovations is their practical nature: they are aimed at developing the ability of innovative thinking in graduates of higher education, as well as students of advanced training courses. So, when we talk about higher education innovation, we mean the new knowledge that is evolving and the innovative vibrancy of education. By innovation enthusiasm, A. K. Markova understands the transformation of new knowledge into a technological or social reality, the transformation of scientific knowledge into a field of goods or services. Characteristic features of innovative education are self-government, professionalism, antropocentrism. The goals of innovative education are: to ensure a high level of spiritual, intellectual and personal development of students; to create conditions for students to acquire scientific thinking skills; to teach the methodology of innovation in the socio-economic and professional spheres. Most educators understand professionalism as follows: the level of skill in finding solutions to professional problems; ability to carry out professional activity; creative approach to non-standard situations, the ability to find a productive solution; intellectual and personal level of development; availability of basic skills and competencies. This means that innovative education puts the educational process in line with the specialization of social and cultural knowledge and skills in the field of technology

(professional culture), which allows him to master the tools and methods of understanding professional problems.

- It should be noted that as a result of the reforms, many advanced innovative technologies have entered the education system. It is this aspect that encourages every teacher to work on themselves and learn new innovative methods. This gave them the opportunity to demonstrate their level of intellectual ability. In the past, the mission of education was to "prepare" people for life by forming knowledge, skills, information and social characteristics, and by adapting individuals to the conditions of society. Today, education does not allow individuals to develop mechanisms of influence that create a balance between society and personal interests, to teach individuals how to improve themselves and find their place in life, to work effectively in society. is being nurtured.
 - World experience shows that the problem of teacher competence has been studied not only in our country, but also by educators, psychologists, methodologists, political scientists, sociologists, philosophers, linguists and other scientists around the world. Accordingly, research scholars interpret pedagogical competence differently in form and content.
 - According to B.D. Elkonin: "Competence means the integration of knowledge, professionalism, qualification, experience, responsibility into pedagogical activity. It means to be a master of your field, to know the secrets of your field. "
 - Thus, today's innovative activity turns the student and the teacher into partners in the educational process. Makes the lesson fun and effective.
 - The development of modern education has given rise to a new direction - innovation. The term "innovative pedagogy" and its specific research originated in Military Europe and the United States in the 1960s. Initially, the innovation activity was led by F.N. Gonobolin, S.M. Godnin, V.I. Zagvyazinskiy, N.V. Kozmina, V.A. Slastenin, A.I. Researched in the works of Shyerbakov. These studies are highlighted in terms of innovative practice practices and the dissemination of best pedagogical practices.X. Barnet, Dj. Bassett, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, M. Mayez, A. Haylock, D. Chen, R. Edem Management of innovation development, organization of changes in education, the necessary conditions for the "life and activity" of innovation issues were analyzed. The psychological aspect of innovation was developed by E. Rodgers, one of the American innovative scientists. He studied the classification of categories of participants in the innovation process, his attitude to innovation, his readiness to perceive it.
 - A number of educators have expressed different views on the term "innovation."
 - In particular, A.I. Prigogin, a researcher in the field of pedagogy, defines "innovation" as a purposeful change that introduces new relatively stable elements into a particular social unit - organization, population, society, group.
 - Researchers A.I. Prigogin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy, A.G. Kruglikov, A.S. Akhiyezer, N.P. Stepanov and others distinguish two approaches to the study of the components of innovation processes:
 - individual micro-level of innovation
 - The level of interaction of individual innovations.
- The first approach highlights a new idea that has been put into practice. The second

approach is understood as the interaction of innovations introduced separately, their unity, competition, and, as a result, the replacement of one by the other.

Scientists distinguish the concept of periodicity of life in the analysis of the microstructure of the innovation process. This is because the concept is a measurable process in relation to innovation.

The pedagogical literature provides a diagram of the innovation process, which includes the following stages:

1. The stage of birth of a new idea or the emergence of a new concept, also called the stage of discovery.
2. Invention, that is, the stage of creating something new.
3. The stage of being able to apply the created innovation in practice.
4. Dissemination of innovation, the stage of its widespread implementation.
5. The dominant stage of innovation in a particular field. At this stage, the novelty loses its novelty, and an effective alternative emerges.
6. The phase of reduction of the scope of innovation by replacement on the basis of a new alternative.

V.A. Slaven believes that innovation is a set of goal-oriented innovation creation, dissemination and use, the goal of which is to meet the needs and aspirations of people by new means.

The role of professional competence in every educator is important. Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for the performance of professional activities and their application in practice at a high level.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area. Competence also requires the constant enrichment of professional knowledge, the ability to learn new information, to understand important social requirements, to be able to search for new information, process it and apply it in their work.

Professional competence is manifested in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- when performing uncertain tasks;
- when using conflicting information;
- being able to have a contingency plan

The introduction of a competency-based approach to general secondary education, which is one of the key components of the system of continuing education, requires special attention to the process of forming the basic and specific competencies of science teachers. Participates in the planning of educational activities, taking into account the psychological characteristics of young teachers, the conditions of the educational institution, makes suggestions for improving the educational process.

As a clear proof of our opinion, the essence of the content of innovative competence in educators is still widely understood today. In particular, the work of each educator is reflected in the following:

- Improving professional BCM;

- critical and creative approach to activities;
- Achieving professional and creative cooperation;
- development of business skills;
- elimination of negative habits;

At the same time, the structural foundations of competence are analyzed as follows:
Special or professional competence (high level of organization of professional activity);
Personal competence (self-development, self-expression);
Individual competence (self-management, professional development and innovation);
Social competence (joint organization of additional activities);

Conclusion

In short, in the process of training and retraining of teachers, as in any field today, the organization and management of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the innovative educational environment, updating the content of education is a requirement of the times. . The above examples are clear evidence of our opinion.

References

- Sayidaxmedov N.S. New pedagogical technologies. - T.: Finance, 2003.
Ochilov M. New pedagogical technologies. - Opposite: Nasaf, 2000
Innovative educational technologies / Muslimov NA, Usmonboyeva MH, Sayfurov DM, Turaev AB - T.: "Sano standart" publishing house, 2015.
Yuldashev JG, Usmanov S. Advanced pedagogical technologies. - T.: Teacher, 2004.
Fayzullayeva N. Pedagogical knowledge - the theoretical basis of the teacher's professionalism // Continuing education. - T.: 2006
Hasanboyev J., Turakulov X.A., Alqarov I., Usmonov N.U. Isyanov RG, Yuzlikayev F. "Theory of pedagogy (Didactics) Tashkent -2011

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